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INFLUENCE OF HEARING LOSS ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN SCHOOL FOR THE DEAF AKWANGA, NASARAWA STATE

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Abstract: *This study aims to examine the impact of hearing impairment on the academic performance of students at the School for the Deaf in Akwanga, Nasarawa State. To guide the research, three objectives and three research questions were formulated. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The population consisted of 45 students with hearing impairment, and the sample was purposively selected from the same group at the School for the Deaf in Akwanga. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed through mean counts and simple percentages. The findings indicate that students effectively schedule and manage their time for reading notes and other learning materials, which helps them balance academic responsibilities with other commitments, thereby positively influencing their performance. Additionally, it was observed that there are no speech therapists, audiologists, or resource rooms available to address the specific needs of students with hearing impairment. The study concludes that the lack of study materials such as sign language textbooks, dictionaries, and equipment like computers, along with the absence of laboratories and playgrounds for sporting activities, as well as the unavailability of speech therapists and resource rooms, adversely affects the academic performance of these students. It is recommended that students with hearing impairment be motivated and encouraged by teachers to explore diverse information resources to expand their knowledge. Teachers should also facilitate frequent reading and writing activities, utilizing appropriate aids to enhance students' academic performance.*

Keywords: Hearing loss, students with hearing impairment, academic performance

Introduction

Around the world, individuals living with disabilities are recognized as a vulnerable group. Disability is defined as an impairment in the structure or function of the human body, which can lead to activity limitations and restrictions in participation (WHO & World Bank, 2011). Globally, approximately 15% of the population lives with some form of disability, with about 360 million people experiencing hearing impairment of all kinds, comprising roughly 91% adults and 9% children (WHO & World Bank, 2011). Persons with hearing impairment are often categorized as deaf or hard of hearing (D/HH), depending on the severity of their hearing loss, which may be permanent or fluctuating and can range from mild hearing loss to profound deafness (Shemesh, 2010).

The sense of hearing is fundamental to nearly all learning experiences individuals encounter. From birth, a baby begins responding to sounds within just a few weeks, a response made possible by the healthy development of their auditory system. Even at a young age, children with well-developed hearing skills can recognize and respond to their parents' voices through auditory discrimination (Nyarko, 2013). Effective learning is greatly enhanced when all five senses, including hearing, work together. Early ability to discriminate and respond to sound stimuli is crucial for the development of a child's auditory system and is often a source of joy for parents.

Societal attitudes towards children with hearing impairments can result in limited exposure to educational opportunities, leading to distinct developmental patterns such as inattentiveness, difficulty completing tasks, and memory issues. As a result, it is often assumed that children with hearing loss will underperform academically. Hearing loss varies in severity—from mild to profound—depending on factors such as the cause, seriousness, and onset.

Academic performance refers to students' achievements across various educational domains, including grades, standardized test scores, and overall educational attainment. The academic success of students with hearing impairment is influenced by multiple factors, including the severity of their hearing loss, age at diagnosis, the level of intervention and support they receive, and the educational environment. Notably, achievements involving reasoning, concepts, abstractions, and mental representations heavily depend on hearing. Children with hearing loss often struggle to associate sounds with objects, which hampers their learning processes. Their modes of learning are limited because they lack this essential cognitive connection. According to WHO (2012), the communication methods used by children with hearing impairment are insufficient to support holistic learning. Relying solely on sight for learning imposes significant limitations, as hearing is a primary sensory channel for communication and information gathering. Its impairment or absence greatly affects how these children access and process information in educational settings.

The provision of education as a social welfare service aims to ensure that individuals with hearing impairments do not feel deprived of privileges and opportunities necessary to become productive, employable, and independent members of society. Kyere (2009) emphasizes that education is a vital tool for empowering the hearing impaired to lead autonomous lives. Empowerment through education begins at the foundational level, where students acquire essential skills and knowledge through structured programs designed to prepare them for higher levels of education (Oduro, 2010). Progress from one educational level to another largely depends on the student's academic performance. Consequently, it is important to place greater emphasis on the academic achievement of all students, including those with hearing impairments.

Hearing loss can lead to social isolation for several reasons. Primarily, children with hearing impairments often experience delayed social development, mainly due to delayed language acquisition. Their inability to perceive auditory social cues also hampers effective social interactions, which can result in increased irritability and social withdrawal. However, children who use sign language or identify with the Deaf culture and attend schools for the deaf may not experience this isolation. Conversely, they may become isolated from their parents if their parents lack knowledge of sign language. This form of social exclusion is especially prevalent in communities where sign language is not widely understood. It is important to recognize that even surrounding communities around schools for the deaf often lack the communication skills necessary to support the learning and social integration of students with hearing impairments.

Akwanga, a town in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, hosts the School for the Deaf Akwanga, which plays a vital role in providing specialized educational services to students with hearing impairments in the region. During my teaching practice at the school in 2019, I observed that the institution struggles with a shortage of teachers, and the needs of students are not adequately met. More attention seems to be given to the hearing-impaired children, while those with other learning disabilities are neglected. Additionally, students in the primary section receive very little support. By primary five, many students still do not know how to sign properly, largely due to the shortage of teachers and the lack of attention from the few available teachers. This is compounded by the fact that, because the school is a boarding institution, all learning is expected to occur within the school environment, yet most parents have little or no knowledge of sign language. It is worth noting that schools are supposed to provide a conducive environment for learning; however, the situation at the School for the Deaf Akwanga is quite the opposite. The classrooms are inadequate and many are not comfortable for students, most lockers are broken, and there are no proper chalkboards to facilitate effective teaching.

Statement of the Problem

The core issue of this study is that students with hearing impairments at the School for the Deaf Akwanga tend to perform poorly academically. This under performance can be linked to a range of factors related to the students themselves, their families, and the educational institutions available to them. A lack of adequate role models and resource persons contributes to delays in developing the abstract reasoning skills necessary for effective academic achievement.

Several studies have shown that, when language is not considered as a basis for assessment or when multiple disabilities are not taken into account, students with hearing impairments possess intelligence levels comparable to their hearing peers. However, in assessment tests, students with hearing impairments often perform worse than their hearing counterparts (Drever & Collins, 2016; Vernon, 2015). These distinct challenges faced by students with hearing impairments are caused by both direct and indirect factors. The low academic achievement observed among these students is therefore associated with influences stemming from the students themselves, their families, and the educational institutions they attend. This study aims to investigate the specific factors that contribute to the poor academic performance of students with hearing impairment at the School for the Deaf Akwanga.

Aim and Objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to find out the effect of hearing loss on academic performance of students with hearing impairment in School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are;

- i. To find out the levels of hearing loss of the students with hearing impairment in School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State.
- ii. To find out the learning habits of the students with hearing impairment in school for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State.
- iii. To find out how parents of students with hearing impairment get involved in the education of their children?
- iv. To find the extent of parental involvement in the education of their children with hearing impairment in School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State.
- v. To examine the availability of learning materials/facilities in the School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State.
- vi. To what extent are required/needed personnel available for teaching students with hearing impairment at the School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State?

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

1. What are the levels of hearing loss on the students with hearing impairment in School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State?
2. What are the learning habits of the students with hearing impairments in School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State?
3. How do parents of students with hearing impairment get involved in the education of their children?
4. What are the necessary learning materials/facilities available in the School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State?
5. Who are the required/needed personnel available for teaching students with hearing impairment at the School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State?

Methodology

Design

Descriptive survey research design was used for this study. This is found suitable for the study because participants' opinions are sought and monitored for possible inferences. According to Awotunde and Ugodulunwa (2014), a survey research study is carried out on a population for the purpose of generalizing the result on the entire population. The design entails the collection and use of data systematically from a given population to describe certain characteristics/features of the population in Akwanga, Nasarawa state.

Population sample size

The population for the study comprised of the entire students with hearing disorders in School for the Deaf, Akwanga with a population of 45 students. This comprises of both primary and secondary section of the school within the age bracket of 7-16 years. The degree of hearing loss includes both severe and profound students with hearing disorder. Considering the population of the study, this research intends to use the total population as its sample. Therefore, the entire students at School for the Deaf Akwanga will constitute the sample for this study. The reason for this sample is for proper inference and adequate generalization of result.

Collection of Data

The instrument for data collection was questionnaire designed by the researcher for students with hearing impairment as well as records containing the results of the students in School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State. The questionnaire will be made up of two sections A and B. Section A will elicit information on students' personal data. Section B will be made up of items for the participants to respond by choosing their level of agreement or disagreement on the effect of hearing impairment on academic performance of students with hearing impairment in School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State. The researcher examined the pupils' files and academic records to see the pattern of their performance in mathematics as compared to other subject areas over a period of time. Descriptive and inferential statistics in analyzing the data collected from the field. To answer the research questions, mean scores in the tables of frequency were used.

Results

Research Question One

What are the levels of hearing loss of the students with hearing impairment in school for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State?

Table 1: Level of Hearing Loss of Students with Hearing Impairment

S/N	Level of Hearing loss	NO	%
1.	Mild	7	15.6%
2.	Moderate	11	24.4%
3.	Severe	22	48.9%
4.	Profound	5	11.1%
Total		45	100

Table 1 show that 7 participants, representing 15.6% have mild hearing loss, 11 participants, representing 24.4% have moderate hearing loss, 22 participants, representing 48.9% have severe hearing loss, and finally 5 participants, representing 11.1% have profound hearing loss

Research Question Two

What are the learning habits of the students with hearing impairments in school for the deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State?

Table 2: Learning Habits of Students with Hearing Impairment.

S/N	Item	Agreed	%	Disagreed	%
1.	I optimize my learning by regularly writing note, reviewing my notes and study materials to strengthen my understanding of the subject	23	51.1	22	48.9
2.	Assistive technology and resources plays a crucial role in supporting my hearing impairment	24	53.3	21	46.7
3.	I set specific learning goals for myself and work diligently to achieve them, taking into consider my hearing impairment and unique learning needs.	32	71.1	13	28.9
4.	I try to expand my knowledge and understanding beyond the classroom through independent research and exploration of various subjects	33	73.3	12	26.7
5.	I effectively manage my time and create a study schedule that allows me to balance my academic responsibilities and other commitments	29	64.4	16	35.6

Table 2 shows the responses of the participants to the research question two on the learning habits of students with hearing impairment in school for the deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State. 23 participants, representing 51.1% agreed that I optimize my learning by regularly writing note, reviewing my notes and study materials to strengthen my understanding of the subject while 22 participants, representing 48.9% disagreed. 24 participants, representing 53.3% agreed that Assistive technology and resources play a crucial role in supporting my hearing impairment while 21 participants, representing 46.7% disagreed. 32 participants representing 71.1% agreed that the set specific learning goals for myself and work diligently to achieve them, taking into consider my hearing impairment and unique learning

needs. While 13 participants, representing 28.9%. Disagreed. 33 participants, representing 73.3% agreed that I try to expand my knowledge and understanding beyond the classroom through independent research and exploration of various subjects while 12 participants, representing 26.7% disagreed. 29 participants, representing 64.4% agreed that I effectively manage my time and create a study schedule that allows me to balance my academic responsibilities and other commitments while 16 participants, representing 35.6% disagreed.

S/N	Item	Agreed	%	Disagreed	%
1.	My Parents regularly attend school meetings and events related to my education, such as parent teachers meeting and workshops	29	64.4	16	36.6
2.	My parents actively engage in discussion with teachers and school staff to monitor my progress and address my educational needs effectively	31	68.9	14	31.1
3.	My parents/guardians encourage and support my involvement in extracurricular activities and school projects, despite my hearing impairment.	26	57.8	19	42.2
4.	My parents provide additional educational resources and materials that support my learning and cater for my specific needs as a student with hearing impairment	23	51.1	22	48.9
5.	My parents assist me with homework, assignment, and studying ensuring that I am able to complete tasks successful despite my hearing impairment.	24	53.3	21	46.7

Research Question Three

How do parents of students with hearing impairment get involved in their children’s education?

Table 3: Parental Involvement in the Education of Students with Hearing Impairment

Table 3 shows the responses of the participants to research question three on how parents of students with hearing impairment get involved in the education of their children. 29 participants, representing 64.4% agreed that their Parents attend school meetings and events, while 16 participants, representing 35.6% disagreed 31 participants, representing 68.9% agreed that their parents actively participate in discussion with teachers and school staff while 14 participants representing 31.1% disagreed. The table also shows that 26 participants, representing 57.8% agreed that their parents/guardians encourage and support to involvement in extracurricular activities and school projects, despite their hearing impairment. While 19 participants, representing 42.2% disagreed.

23 participants, representing 51.1% agreed that their parents provide educational resources and materials that support their learning and cater for their specific needs as a student while 22 participants, representing 48.9% disagreed. The table finally shows that 24 participants, representing

53.3% agreed that their parents assist them with homework, assignment, and studying ensuring that they are able to complete tasks successful despite their hearing impairment while 21 participants, representing 46.7% disagreed with the statement.

Research Question Four

What are the necessary leaning materials/ facilities available in the School for the Deaf Akwanga Nasarawa State?

Table 4: Availability of Learning Materials/ Facilities in the School for the Deaf

S/N	Materials/ facilities	Available	%	Not Available	%
1.	Library	18	40	27	60
2.	Textbooks	31	68.9	14	31.1
3.	Sign language dictionary	14	31.1	31	68.9
4.	Computers	0	0	45	100
5.	Science Lab	7	15.6	38	84.4
6	Play areas	7	15.6	38	84.4
7	Cafeteria	45	100	0	0
8	Work books	37	82.2	8	17.8

Table 4 shows that 18 participants, representing 40% agreed that there is a library in their school while 27 participants, representing 60% said that there is no library in their school. 31 participants, representing 68.9% agreed that there are textbooks in their school while 14 participants, representing 31.1% agreed that there are no textbooks in their school. 14 participants representing 31.1% agreed that there are sign language dictionaries in their school. 31 participants, representing 68.9% agreed that there are no sign language dictionaries in their school. None of the participants, agreed that there are computers in their school. This means that all the 45 participants, representing 100% agreed that there are no computers in their school.

The table shows that 7 participants representing 15.6% agreed that there are science laboratories in their school while 38 participants, representing 84.4% agreed that there are no science laboratories in their school. 7 participants representing 15.6% agreed that there are play areas in their school while 38 participants representing 84.4% agreed that there are no play areas in their school. 45 participants representing 100% agreed that there is a cafeteria in their school. This means none of the participants, said that there is no cafeteria in their school. 37 participants, representing 82.2% agreed that there are available workbooks in their school while 8 participants, representing 17.8% agreed that there no available workbooks in their school.

Research Question Five

Who are the required/ needed personnel available for teaching students with hearing impairment at the School for the Deaf Akwanga, Nasarawa State?

Table 5: Available of Required/Needed Personnel for Teaching Students with Hearing Impairment

S/N	STAFF	Available	%	Not Available	%
1.	Interpreters	33	73.3	12	26.7
2.	Speech therapist	21	46.7	24	53.3
3.	Audiologist	17	37.8	28	62.2
4.	Guidance and counselor	31	68.9	14	31.1
5.	Resource teachers / specialist	7	15.6	38	84.4

Table 5 shows that 33 participants, representing 73.3% agreed that there are interpreters in their school while 12 participants, representing 26.7% said that there are no interpreters in their school. 21 participants, representing 46.7% agreed that there is speech therapist in their school while 24 participants, representing 53.3% agreed that there is no speech therapist in their school. 17 participants, representing 37.8% agreed that there are Audiologists in their school while 28 participants, representing 62.2% said that there are no audiologists in their school. The table also shows that 31 participants, representing 68.9% agreed that there are available guidance and counselor in their school while 14 participants, representing 31.1% agreed that there are no guidance and counselor in their school. Finally, the table shows that 7 participants, representing 15.6% agreed that there are Resource teachers/Specialists in their school while 38 participants, representing 84.4% agreed that there are no Resource teachers/Specialist in their school.

Discussion

The research revealed that 15.6% of the participants have mild hearing loss, 11 participants representing 24.4% have moderate hearing loss, 22 participants, representing 48.9% have severe hearing loss, and finally 5 participants, representing 11.1% have profound hearing loss. The study revealed the learning habits of the students with hearing impairment were that they reviewed their notes and study materials. They set specific goals for themselves and they create a study schedule as well as manage their time for reading. These habits enabled to balance their academic responsibilities and other commitments which aided their performance.

The table also revealed that many parents attend school meetings and events, actively participate in discussions with teachers and school staff as well as encourage and support their children's involvement in extracurricular activities and school projects, despite their hearing impairment.

The study further revealed that many parents provide educational resources and materials that support their specific needs as students, and they also assist with homework, assignments and studying ensuring that they are able to complete task successfully despite their hearing impairment.

The study revealed that though there is a library in the school, the learning materials for the students with hearing impairments are not adequate. There no sign language dictionaries in the school, no computers, no laboratories, and no play areas. On the issue of availability of facilities and learning materials, the study revealed that there are textbooks and workbooks in the school. The school also has a cafeteria for the students.

Concerning availability of the needed personnel, the study showed that there are interpreters for students with hearing impairment in the school. There is also a guidance counselor but there are a few speech therapist, audiologist, and no resource room for specialists to attend to the needs of the students with hearing impairment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusion could be drawn;

Poor learning habits interest of students with hearing impairment affects their performance in English language and mathematics and in turn affect their academic responsibilities and other commitments in the school. Family background of students with hearing impairment also affects their performance, therefor, parents have significant role to play in the academic performance of students with hearing impairment by providing educational resources and materials that support the specific needs of these students to help them achieve the desired performance in their academic work.

Finally, lack of studying materials like; sign language textbooks, dictionaries, other equipment such as computers, lack of laboratories, playground for sporting activities and the absence of a speech therapist and resource room have an adverse effect on the performance of students with hearing impairment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher makes the following recommendations:

1. Students with hearing impairment should be motivated and encouraged by their teachers to read different information resources to broaden their knowledge.
2. Teacher should engage the students in frequent reading and writing activities through the use of aids to enhance their performance.
3. Parents should encourage their children with hearing impairment to start reading at an early age by having a mini library as well as favourable reading environment at home.
4. Government/School authorities should provide library and equip them with the needed learning materials
5. Government should motivate special teachers by giving them special allowances to boost their morale.
6. Schools should provide computer assistive technology for use by the students with hearing impairment. In this regard, non-governmental organizations should donate assistive technology devices to schools for the benefit of the students with hearing impairment.

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